

2-[Effort-Threshold](Reviewer#A#B)

20% is widely treated as the effort threshold [38,43] in effort-aware settings. To comprehensively study how effort thresholds impact the performance of JIT-Fine and baselines, we conduct another experiment to investigate the relationship between different threshold and models' performances.

We set effort threshold from 10% to 100% with a step of 5%, and conduct experiments on both JIT-DP and JIT-DL considering two effort-aware performance measures (i.e., Recall@K%Effort and Effort@K%Recall)

As for JIT-DP, since our approach JIT-Fine is similar to JITLine and the limitation of time, we only conduct a comparison study between JIT-Fine and JITLine.

As for JIT-DL, we compare JIT-Fine with both JIT-Fine and Yan et al [59].

We find that different effort thresholds have impact on effort-aware performance measures and our approach JIT-Fine always perform better than baselines on both JIT-DP and JIT-DL.

JIT-DP results:

Fig 1. Comparison between JIT-Fine and JITLine on JIT-DP

As shown in Fig 1, the x-axis represents the values of different effort threshold, while the y-axis represents the performance values.

From the results shown in the two sub-figures, we find that JIT-Fine always perform better than JITLine on different effort threshold settings.

JIT-DL results:

Fig 2. Comparison between JIT-Fine and JITLine on JIT-DL

As shown in Fig 2, the x-axis represents the values of different effort threshold, while the y-axis represents the performance values.

From the results shown in the two sub-figures, we find that JIT-Fine always perform better than both JITLine and Yan et al. on different effort threshold settings.

Reviewer#C

C1-[C-Q1-Buggy Line Distribution]

Response:

We first analyze how the buggy line distributes among commits on testing dataset, then analyze how the buggy lines distribution affects the performance of JIT-Fine.

Fig C-1: The distribution of buggy line

Fig C-1(a) shows the buggy lines distribution including the ratio between buggy lines and all lines in each commit and the count of commits in the distribution in different buggy line ratio ranges.

In Fig C-1(a), the bottom x-axis shows the index of commits, while the top x-axis shows the different buggy lines ratio range, the left y-axis shows the numbers of commits, and the right y-axis shows the buggy lines ratio.

Accordingly, in Fig C-1(b), we show the numbers of buggy lines, the numbers of all lines as well as the buggy lines ratio distribution.

Notice that we here only present the commits correctly predicted by our approach JIT-Fine and we sort all commits by buggy lines ratio in descending.

According to the results, we find that most commits have a high ratio of buggy lines.

Localization performance of JIT-Fine on commit with different buggy line ratios

Fig C-2: The five performances of JIT-Fine among commits with varying buggy lines ratio

Fig C-2 shows the five performances (i.e., (a) of IFA, (b) of Effort@20%Recall, (c) Recall@20%Effort, (d)Top-5, and (e) of Top-10) of JIT-Fine among commits with varying buggy lines ratio. In which, the x-axis shows the index of commit, the left y-axis shows the value of each performance, and the right y-axis shows the buggy line ratio. For easy comparison, we also sort commits by buggy line ratio in descending.

As for IFA in Fig C-2(a), we find that the higher buggy line ratio a commit has, the better performance of IFA JIT-Fine obtains.

As for Effort@20%Recall in Fig C-2(b), JIF-Fine performs differently on commits with different buggy line ratios.

As for Recall@20%Effort in Fig C-2(c), JIT-Fine performs similarly to the ones on Effort@20%Recall, but overall, JIT-Fine can obtain a higher performance of Recall@20%Effort as the buggy line ratios decrease on commits.

As for Top-5 and Top-10 in Fig C-2(d) and Fig C-2(d), JIT-Fine achieves better performance on commits with a higher buggy line ratio and performs down as the buggy line ratio of commits decreases.

